

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Central- Eastern European Consensus Statement on Breast Cancer Radiotherapy

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A Central -Eastern European consensus conference on breast cancer was held in Visegrad (Hungary) in November 2021. with the participation of 21 countries and an international guideline for breast cancer diagnosis and treatment was created. Radiotherapy of Breast cancer-Professional Guideline 1st Central-Eastern European Professional Consensus Statement on Breast Cancer was published in Pathology and Oncology Research Journal in June 2022. Radiotherapy (RT) after breast conserving surgery (BCS) is indicated in ductal carcinoma in situ (stage 0) and in early stage (stage I-II) of invasive breast cancer. In elderly patients with stage I and hormone receptor positive tumor, RT can be omitted if hormonal therapy is prescribed. Hypofractionated whole breast irradiation is validate treatment alternative to conventional fractionation. Accelerated partial breast irradiation is indicated in low-risk patients using interstitial brachytherapy or external beam RT.

Post-mastectomy radiotherapy significantly decreases the risk of recurrence and improves survival in node-positive patients. After neoadjuvant systemic treatment (NST) followed by BCS, irradiation of the whole breast is mandatory and after mastectomy, locoregional RT is recommended if initial stage was III-IV and ypN1 axillary status.

International guidelines for breast cancer radiotherapy are desirable in the light of fast technology development and increasing use of systemic therapy.

Keywords: breast cancer, professional guideline, radiotherapy

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